

QUIZ

LAST NAME: Edeh

FIRST NAME: Ini

PROGRAM CODE: ACA-401D

COURSE CODE : PHGH

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INSTRUCTOR: Dr Gulma

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. Which of the following is not true of style guides?

- Aspects of grammar they address include punctuation, vocabulary, spelling, abbreviations.
- They are generally associated with certain types of writing such as technical, commercial or business writing.
- They ensure consistency in writing style where there are many contributing authors.
- Several debates have led to the development of a standard authoritative style for written reports.¹**

2. When paraphrasing another author's words one of these is considered plagiarism which is a serious academic offence.

- Re-writing the idea in other words with adequate citation.

¹ Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-40/ACA-401D Coursepack, Period 1*. Second edition (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 24.

- Expressing the idea in completely different words without citation.²**
 - Using a writing style that is different from the author's though there is proper citation.
 - Accurately representing an author's information in a different format with proper citation.
3. **The WHO style guide which is also called 'house style', confers certain advantages which does not include one of the following:**
- Increased access to funding.³**
 - Consistency in manner of presentation of documents.
 - Increased efficiency of its editing process.
 - Maintenance of a single corporate image.
4. **The WHO house style insists on use of non-discriminatory language because**
- Funding and support for the organization is tied to it.
 - Majority of the reader's/user's of their manuals have one disability or the other.
 - It desires to address everyone fairly and equally without causing offence.⁴**
 - It is a legal requirement for all international health/social organizations.

²Cleenewerck and Gulma, 8

³World Health Organization. *WHO style guide*. (Geneva: WHO, 2004), 1

⁴World Health Organization, 55

5. **One of the following is not a feature of an acceptable research report**

- Credibility of the evidence.
- Trustworthy reasoning.
- Independent truths.
- Spiritual truths and intuition.⁵**

6. **Different sources provide materials for research. Which of the following is not true of sources for research information?**

- Primary sources should be the main source for evidence and can include private diaries, images and recordings.
- Primary sources are only accepted if they have been published and are in the public domain.⁶**
- Other research works serve as secondary sources and are valuable sources from which to learn more about a topic.
- Tertiary sources of information generally provide introductory overviews and are usually written for non-specialist audiences.

7. **Research is based on questions and there are different types of research questions used in different fields of study. One of the following is not a valid type of research question.**

- Operational question.⁷**
- Conceptual question.
- Practical question.

⁵ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eight Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, Revised by Wayne C. Booth et al, Eight edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 15.

⁶Kate L. Turabian, 25

⁷Kate L. Turabian, 16-17

- Applied question

8. **Which of this is not a correct reason for citing sources?**

- To give credit.
- To assure your readers of the accuracy of your facts.
- To show the depth of your research work.⁸**
- To help readers follow or even extend your work.

9. **The purpose statement is the major objective or intent of the study. Which of these statements is true of the purpose statement?**

- It should put the literature review in context.
- It should be written in clear and concise language.⁹**
- It should be repeated in several different ways.
- It is usually written at the end of the work in order to capture all aspects

10. **An abstract is an essential part of the research report often written at the end of the work. One of the following is not expected to be found in the abstract.**

- The research questions.¹⁰**
- The key findings, conclusions and recommendations.

⁸Kate L. Turabian, 86

⁹Bloomberg, Linda Dale and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. (California: SAGE publications, 2008), 35

¹⁰ Bloomberg and Volpe, 168

- The title of the study.
- The methods and procedures data collection and analysis.

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